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The Relationship of Transformational Leadership and Organizational Culture with Creativity in the Employees of Sport and Youth Ministry

Maryam Mokhtari Dinani^{1*}

Abstract

The aim of this study was to investigate the relationship of sport managers' transformational leadership style and organizational culture of Ministry of Sport and Youth with the creativity of the employees of this ministry. The research method was descriptive-correlation and statistical population included 950 managers and employees of the Ministry of Sport and Youth. According to the Morgan and Krejcie Table and using stratified random sampling method, 274 subjects were selected as the sample. Torrance (1959) Creativity Questionnaire, Denison (2000) Organizational Culture Questionnaire and Bass and Olive (2000) Leadership Style Questionnaire were used to collect data. For data analysis, simple and multiple regressions were used. The results showed that managers' leadership style in sport and organizational culture of sport organizations had a significant and positive relationship with employees' creativity in these organizations ($P \leq 0.05$) and these two variables had the ability to predict employees' creativity.

Keywords: creativity, leadership style, manager, organizational culture, transformational.

¹ . Assistant Professor of Alzahra University, Email: M.mokhtaridinani@alzahra.ac.ir